

Monastery of saint Neophytos the Recluse

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Religious Place, Orthodoxy, Monasticism, Cyprus, Paphos

Saint Neophytos was born in 1134 in Cyprus. He was tonsured at the Monastery of saint Chrysostom Koutsoventis (Cyprus). Following a great deal of wanderings, in 1159 he found a cave in the mountains of Paphos (near the present-day village of Tala) where he was settled and lived until the end of his life (ca. 1214) as a recluse. By 1160 Neophytos widened the original cave (the Enkleistra) and removed the insecure parts, he set up an altar, dedicated to the Holy Cross, and excavated a tomb, in which he was buried after his death. By 1170 Neophytos was a well-known hermit, so at the instigation of the bishop of Paphos Basil Kinnamos, he accepted priesthood and founded a monastery, for which he composed a set of rules ("Typiki Diathiki") for its administration. Following this decision, the cave was extended for the creation of cells and the refectory. In 1183 was created the naos. As indicated by the inscription in the cell written by the well-known painter Theodoros Apseudis, another part of the cell and the tomb chamber were decorated under the patronage of Basil Kinnamos, between 1182 and 1183. The frescoes covered the original, simple, white ground fresco decoration. Apart from the scene of the Annunciation, the rest of the Christological scenes from this phase of decoration, belong to the Passion cycle. The rest of the walls are covered with representations of monastic saints holding scrolls, on which are written didactic passages. The fact that saint Neophytos was depicted twice in the program could indicate that he was the person who determined it, instead of the patron, Basil Kinnamos. By the end of 1197 was completed the so-called "New Zion", a cave above the initial cell of the Enkleistra, dug and named thus by Neophytos, who was constantly longing for solitude. After Neophytos moved to the upper cell, the iconostasis was inserted, and the naos was decorated with more monastic saints by another painter. Around 1200 the refectory was decorated by a different painter. After the saint's death, the monastic community continued to exist. Around 1500 the narthex was remodelled and decorated, and the refectory was partially repainted. In 1503 the paintings in the naos and the bema have been partially restored. In the early 16th century, in the vicinity of the Enkleistra was built the new katholikon (main church) of the monastery, dedicated to the Virgin Mary. It is a three-aisled basilica ending in a large apse to the east. The lateral aisles are divided from the central nave by colonnades. The nave and the aisles are barrel-vaulted. The nave vault is interrupted before the sanctuary by a dome on high drum. The doorway on the west wall, as well as the plain lancet windows follow Gothic models. The church was entirely decorated with frescoes, a large part of which was destroyed. In the middle of the eighteenth century, the relics of Neophytos were translated to the church, where they are housed until today. Around the Enkleistra and the katholikon of the Monastery were erected in different periods auxiliary buildings including cells for the monks, the refectory, a library, a museum etc.

Date Range: 1159 CE - 1503 CE

Region: Monastery of Saint Neophytos

Region tags: Cyprus, Paphos

The Monastery of Saint Neophytos in Paphos, Cyprus

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Indianos, A., Thomson, G.H., "Wall paintings at St. Neophytos Monastery", *Kypriakai Spoudai* 3 (1940), 155-224
- Source 2: Mango, C., Hawkins, E., "The Hermitage of St. Neophytos and its Wall Paintings", *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 20 (1966) 119–206
- Source 3: Tsiknopoulos, I., *Ὁ ἅγιος Νεόφυτος καὶ ἡ ἱερά αὐτοῦ μονή*, Paphos 1955

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.doaks.org/research/byzantine/project-grants/kakoulli-fischer-2011-2012>
- Source 1 Description: The Techniques and Materials of the Wall Paintings at the Enkleistra of St. Neophytos
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.doaks.org/research/byzantine/project-grants/kakoulli-and-fischer-2008-2009>
- Source 2 Description: An Innovative Noninvasive and Nondestructive Multidisciplinary Approach for the Technical Study of the Byzantine Wall Paintings in the Enkleistra of St. Neophytos in Paphos, Cyprus

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Cave

Type of elevation

- Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Leveling of ground
 - Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

- ↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- No

Notes: However, houses were built some kilometres away from the Monastery during the last decades.

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Notes: When saint Neophytos was settled, the place was indeed far removed from every habitation. During the last decades houses were built some kilometres away from the Monastery.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

- ↳ A single structure

- No

- ↳ One single feature

- Other [specify]: The Monastery is composed by a group of caves and a 16th-century church surrounded by the auxiliary buildings of the Monastery

- ↳ A group of structures:

- Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Enkleistra of Saint Neophytos and the Katholikon dedicated to the Mother of God belong to the Monastery of Saint Neophytos.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: The Enkleistra was the living space of a monastic community created around saint Neophytos the Recluse. It included also a space of worship dedicated to the Holy Cross. The katholikon built ca. 1500 is dedicated exclusively to the worship of the monastic community until today.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The Enkleistra started as a single cave and was expanded. At the beginning of the 16th century was built the katholikon of the Monastery. Over the last century, the exterior of the Enkleistra underwent interventions for being made accessible. Furthermore, auxiliary buildings were built.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: To saint Neophytos the Recluse, since this was the place where he lived, as well as the place where his relics are housed. Yet, the Katholikon of the Monastery is dedicated to the Mother of God.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Monastery is generally known as the "Enkleistra of saint Neophytos the Recluse". Yet, the altar of the Enkleistra was dedicated to the Holy Cross, while the main church of the Monastery is dedicated to the Mother of God.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

Notes: The relics of saint Neophytos were moved from his tomb in the 18th century. They are currently housed in the main church of the monastery.

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: It is estimated that the paintings of the Enkleistra is the work of at least 3 or 4 painters. We only know the name of Theodoros Apseudis who decorated a part of the cell and the tomb chamber between 1182 and 1183.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The paintings by Theodoros Apseudis were funded by the bishop of Paphos, Basil Kinnamos.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Enkleistra was initially created as a place of solitude and prayer by saint Neophytos. He included in the cave an altar for the celebration of the holy liturgy. More cells were created in the rock for accommodating the monastic community established around Neophytos. Around 1500 the new church was built.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The Enkleistra was dug into the original cave where saint Neophytos was installed.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The different spaces that compose the Enkleistra communicate between them and are all dug into the rock of the mountain.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Notes: The two structures, the Enkleistra and the katholikon, have a different purpose. The Enkleistra accommodates rarely services, while the everyday liturgies of the monastic community are taking place in the 16th-century katholikon of the Monastery.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments for the frescoes executed in both structures (Enkleistra and katholikon).

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Frescoes.

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon of the Monastery and the Enkleistra include an iconostasis and icons, as well as wooden furniture.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels and saints.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Notes: Yet, when Neophytos was represented was not sanctified.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Orthodox churches contain panel paintings that represent Saints and

scenes from the Life of Christ and the Virgin, as well as of the Saints.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Notes: True fresco is present both in the Enkleistra and in the katholikon.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ, the Virgin and from the life of Saints.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: They are purely informative. They indicate the scene or the saint depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The inscriptions of both the Enkleistra and the katholikon of the Monastery are not exceptional. Like all inscriptions juxtaposing scenes or effigies, their aim is to inform the viewer on the person or scene depicted.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Saints and angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: In the Enkleistra saint Neophytos is depicted between Archangels leading him to Christ on the Day of Judgment.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Cross.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the life of Christ and the Virgin.

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: It is not a tomb. Yet, it includes the tomb of saint Neophytos.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb of saint Neophytos is currently a cenotaph, since the corpse was moved to the

katholikon in the 18th century.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: As is the case of every monastery, the monks/members of the community are buried at the cemetery of the monastery.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The example of saint Neophytos who prepared his tomb in such a small space dug into the rock of the mountain is not a common one.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes during prayer and during the liturgies and the various services.

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Faithful and pilgrims are visiting the Monastery of Saint Neophytos to pray.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Via prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: With saints, via prayer.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: They can be composed of valuable objects but also of objects without material value, or of small value such as bread, wine and olive-oil for the services.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to a Christian Orthodox Monastery can be anything.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There is absolutely no rule imposing faithful or pilgrims to make an offering to Christian Orthodox monasteries.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for the conservation and restoration of the Enkleistra by specialists such as engineers, archaeologists etc.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery exists since the 12th century so there were inevitably repairs/reconstructions and there will be also in the future.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: It is performed by the monks of the monastic community but also by experts.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Monastery is considered one of the most important monuments of Cyprus, so it attracts an important number of visitors. Maintenance is also necessary for being able to accommodate them.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Notes: No there are not. Yet, pilgrims visit the Monastery for the feast of saint Neophytos on January 24 and September 28.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Services and the liturgy are taking place at the katholikon as prescribed for Christian Orthodox monastic communities.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Impossible to specify

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: There are between 2-4 services per day.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Orthodox liturgy and the various services are synchronic practices

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: The monastic community is living at the monastery.

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male monastic community.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The superior of the Monastery is responsible for the community. He is assisted by the council of the monastic community, generally composed by the oldest members, or those that have the longest experience as monks.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery is still functioning and a monastic community is living at the place.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, saint Neophytos was a prolific writer who composed his biography, an account of the first years of the Latin conquest of the island, as well as several theological treatises.

Bibliography

General References

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